

Critical Density Iteration — An Improved Critical Density Search Algorithm in OpenMC

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ABSTRACT

Balance of neutron production and losses in nuclear reactors is crucial for their stable operation. In pressurized water reactors control rods are used for short term control; and boric acid dissolved in the cooling water is used for compensating slow reactor fuel composition changes. Reactor design operation rely heavily on simulations to ensure optimal performance and safe operation. High accuracy simulations need precisely defined material compositions, which is not trivial for ever-changing fuel compositions, that require frequent boric acid concentration adjustment. Critical density is the concentration of boric acid, where the neutron loss equals neutron production.

This paper presents a Critical Density Iterations (CDI) implementation in OpenMC, a Monte Carlo neutron transport code, which allows for accurate determination of critical density. The algorithm is based on iterating material concentrations changes provided by the neutron balance equation and refined by the Kalman filter. Kalman filtering allows for more accurate and reliable iteration convergence, by also considering previous iteration steps.

CDI is compared to the current search algorithms in OpenMC by simulating a generic simplified PWR reactor core, which is serving as a testing framework. CDI finds the critical density with 5 to 10 times fewer simulated neutrons and is more resilient to stochastic deviations from Monte Carlo simulation results. Other improvements also allow for more user-friendly material nuclide enrichment-based mixing.

Keywords: OpenMC, Monte Carlo, Nuclear energy, Critical density, Algorithm

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear reactors mass of fissile atoms is converted into heat by neutron induced fissions. Their operation relies on maintaining balance between neutron production and loss, ensuring a sustained and controlled chain reaction. Current generation of reactors have to be actively controlled to maintain constant reactor power, which is linearly connected with the number of free neutrons present in the reactor, where we assume that the neutron spectrum remains constant. On short timescales in Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs) any deviations in neutron population are compensated by inserting or removing neutron absorbing control rods. Compensation of slow fuel burnup composition changes in PWRs is done by diluting boric acid dissolved in water coolant. The density of boric acid where neutron population remains constant is called critical boric acid density. Critical density in operational reactors is calculated quickly using deterministic methods, based on previous simulations, whereas Monte Carlo (MC) methods are used mainly in research when exploring unknown conditions.

Due to ever-changing reactor material compositions, frequent computations of critical boric acid density need to be fast and efficient. Few different algorithms have been developed in the past, mostly of numerical nature; namely bisection and higher order search algorithms. During reactor simulations various parameters can be extracted, which can be used to speed up convergence and improve resilience.

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To date, only numerical algorithms have been implemented in OpenMC [1], a MC neutron transport code. They complete the whole neutron transport simulation and only then after change the nuclide densities, which is inefficient and time consuming. In this paper we developed an improved critical density iteration (CDI) search algorithm based on one implemented in SERPENT [2, 3], that intertwines the search algorithm within a single, albeit approximately 30% longer, simulation. We incorporated the Kalman filter for measuring a scalar constant [4] into the algorithm to improve estimations of critical concentrations simulations, by also considering previous steps within the algorithm intertwined simulation. Combining multiple estimations reduces uncertainty and the required number of iterations for the algorithm to converge. Compared to current numerical algorithms, CDI is more resilient to statistical noise resulting from the MC method, and is more appropriate for use in MC codes.

2. CRITICAL DENSITY ITERATION

2.1. Theoretical Background

Changes in the reactor's neutron population can be described by the neutron balance equation (1). Any deviation from balance results in change of neutron population, the factor for which the neutron population changes between two neutron generations is called effective neutron multiplication factor (k_{eff}). Neutron population is defined by the number of neutrons in the reactor at any given time. Two consecutive neutron populations constitute successive generations: neutrons in the parent generation are either absorbed, leak from the reactor, or induce fission, producing the next generation. Reactors operate at constant powers then need to be exactly critical — maintain their effective neutron multiplication factor equal to one; $k_{eff} \equiv 1.0000\dots$, or in other words balance neutron production and losses.

Due to short neutron lifetimes on the order of a few milliseconds and their high numbers inside the reactor core $\approx 10^{10} \frac{\text{neutrons}}{\text{cm}^3}$ exact simulations are infeasible. That is why MC simulations were invented to simulate a population sample and extrapolate the results to the whole population. Neutron population is simulated in generations with equal number of simulated neutrons, where k_{eff} can be extracted through the neutron balance equation:

$$\frac{1}{k_{eff}} P_{fiss} + P_{n xn} = L_{abs} + L_{leak}. \quad (1)$$

Left side of Equation (1) represents neutron production rate (index P) and the right side neutron loss rate (index L), specifically:

- P_{fiss} represents neutron production rate due to fission; $\bar{\nu} \Sigma_f \phi$,
- $P_{n xn}$ represents neutron production rate due to (n, xn) reactions; $\sum_{x=2}^{\infty} (x-1) \cdot \Sigma_{(n, xn)} \phi$,
- L_{abs} represents neutron loss rate due to absorption (including fission, neutron capture, (n, xn) reactions, ...); $\Sigma_a \phi$, and
- L_{leak} represents neutron loss rate due to leakage from the system; $\approx DB^2$.

$\bar{\nu}$ is the average number of released neutrons per fission, ϕ is scalar neutron flux, $\Sigma_f, \Sigma_a, \Sigma_{(n, xn)}$ are macroscopic fission, absorption and (n, xn) reaction cross-sections, D is average neutron diffusion coefficient, and B is the geometric buckling of the reactor. Atomic densities of nuclides n_i , where i runs through all isotopes, in the reactor are a part of macroscopic cross-section $\Sigma_x = \sum_{i=\text{nuclide}} n_i \sigma_{x,i}$.

Neutron absorption can be further divided into two parts; $L_{abs} = (L_{abs} - L_{abs, nucs}) + L_{abs, nucs}$:

- $L_{abs, nucs}$ — flagged nuclides of interest in CDI; $\Sigma_{a, nucs} \phi \equiv \sum_{i=\text{nuclide}} n_{i, nucs} \sigma_{a,i} \phi$, and
- $(L_{abs} - L_{abs, nucs})$ — all other nuclides; $(\Sigma_a - \Sigma_{a, nucs}) \phi$.

$n_{i, nucs}$ is the atom number density of flagged nuclide i and $\sigma_{a,i}$ its microscopic absorption cross-section.

The goal of the algorithm is to modify densities of flagged nuclides and achieve the desired k_{eff} . We assume that nuclide densities and their neutron absorption rate are linearly dependent. We can estimate

the target flagged nuclide absorption rate $L_{abs,nucs}^{tgt}$ by rearranging Equation (1):

$$L_{abs,nucs}^{tgt} = \frac{1}{k_{eff}^{tgt}} P_{fiss} + P_{nxs} - L_{leak} - (L_{abs} - L_{abs,nucs}). \quad (2)$$

Using Equation (2) and the linear relation approximation between $L_{abs,nucs}$ and flagged nuclide atom number densities $n_{i,nucs}$, we estimate the scaling factor (g) for flagged nuclides:

$$g = \frac{n_{i,nucs}^{tgt}}{n_{i,nucs}} = \frac{L_{abs,nucs}^{tgt}}{L_{abs,nucs}}. \quad (3)$$

In the simulation model we update flagged nuclide in each simulation step (batch). Process of iteratively changing nuclide concentrations and simulating batches of neutron transport (to update neutron production and loss rate) converges to desired flagged nuclide densities. As a result the effective neutron multiplication factor k_{eff} should also converge to the desired value of k_{eff}^{tgt} .

2.2. Kalman Filtering

The algorithm described in the previous section is the algorithm implemented in MC neutron transport code SERPENT [3]. Each iteration returns an independent estimation of critical boric acid density. Due to the stochastic nature of MC simulation, the estimated values of critical density will fluctuate around the true value. By considering previous simulation steps the estimation can be improved and the statistical uncertainty reduced. We assume the simulation's measured estimates follow a normal (Gaussian) distribution. The optimal way to merge two normally distributed measurements ($z_1 \pm \sigma_1$, $z_2 \pm \sigma_2$) is:

$$\hat{x} = z_1 + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2} (z_2 - z_1); \quad \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_1^2} + \frac{1}{\sigma_2^2} \quad (4)$$

The process can be iterated for multiple subsequent normally distributed measurements ($\hat{x}_m \pm \hat{\sigma}_m$, $z_{m+1} \pm \sigma_m$), yielding the Kalman filter for measuring a constant scalar value:

$$x_{m+1}^{\hat{}} = \hat{x}_m + \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{m+1}^2}{\sigma_m^2} (z_{m+1} - \hat{x}_m); \quad \frac{1}{\sigma_{m+1}^{\hat{}}} = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_m^2} + \frac{1}{\sigma_m^2} \quad (5)$$

Now we apply the Kalman filter to the critical density iteration for flagged nuclides with density $n_{i,nucs}$, where we determine flagged nuclide critical density value $z_{m+1} = n_{i,nucs,m} g_m$; we obtain scaling factor g_m from the above described balance algorithm in Equation (3).

2.3. Algorithm Implementation

The CDI algorithm is implemented in *Python* API of the OpenMC. Although neutron transport is run by the C side of OpenMC, we are able to update material nuclide densities in between neutron transport batches through the shared material nuclide density matrix in computer memory.

The algorithm can determine critical densities for single nuclides, multiple nuclides of the same element, and for molecules (i.e., groups of nuclides). Critical density iteration can change flagged nuclide concentrations either in all materials or just in specifically flagged materials, or it allows for material mixing function provided by the user. OpenMC runs neutron transport simulations in two parts:

- Inactive part: Preparation for the active part of the simulation. Here neutron flux's spatial and energy distributions converge.
- Active part: Simulation is run in full.

Results can be tallied in the inactive transport too, but they are discarded when the active part of the simulation starts. For that reason, we are able to complete the critical density iteration in the inactive

neutron transport. All required values for calculation of critical densities are obtained either from internal OpenMC tallies (k_{eff} , leakage fraction) or from custom tallies for flagged nuclides in flagged materials and the whole simulation. Extracting values from batchwise cumulative tallies is easy and achieved by calculating the difference between the current and previous simulated batch results.

The algorithm tracks the total scaling factor of nuclide densities after N batches:

$$f = \prod_{m=1}^N g_m; \quad n_{i,nucs} = n_{i,nucs_0} \cdot f \quad (6)$$

which can be calculated without knowing initial concentrations $n_{i,nucs_0}$. Optionally the initial value of concentrations can be fed into the algorithm to get easily readable results. Another option connected with the initial value is the search bracket, if we want to limit the search to a certain concentration value range. Number of extra batches to be performed by the critical density algorithm can also be defined by the user, by default the value is 50, which balances the convergence requirements and reduction in uncertainty. Of course, the optimal number of batches depends on the specifics of each problem case.

2.3.1. Uncertainty propagation

Since each batch is a part of the MC simulation, its results or tallies have uncertainties. Standard deviation of Gaussian measurements falls with the square root of number of measurements. Applied to MC simulation, the estimated standard deviation scales as $\sigma_x \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_x}}$, where N_x is the number of tallied particles, for example the count of absorption events on the flagged nuclides. The number of events is automatically normalized to number of reactions per source particle.

These uncertainties can be easily accurately estimated using the balance equation (1). We know that for each simulated batch all neutrons have to be either absorbed or escape the reactor for the batch simulation to end. Therefore, the relative uncertainty of neutron losses is $\delta_{loss} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_M}}$, where N_M is the number of neutrons in a batch. Since all tallied reactions that lead to neutron loss, they can be represented as a fraction of all the neutron losses: $\delta_{L_x} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_M}} \sqrt{\frac{N_M}{N_x}}$. And $\frac{N_M}{N_x}$ is the same as $\frac{L}{L_x}$, where L_x is the tally obtained from the simulation and $L = \sum_x L_x$. Tally's standard deviation is calculated using:

$$\sigma_{L_x} = \delta_{L_x} L_x = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_M}} \sqrt{L L_x}. \quad (7)$$

$\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_M}}$ is tally independent as it is only dependent on user provided number of simulated neutrons per batch (N_M). The same logic can be applied to the production tallies $P = \sum_x P_x$. The rest of uncertainty propagation also considering Kalman filter to the final σ is either trivial or has already been discussed. Note that statistical deviations of subsequent estimations is correlated, due to generational evolution of MC neutron transport simulations; i.e. locally increased neutron flux statistical fluctuation in fuel that increases P_{fiss} . Relative strength of this effect diminishes with increasing number of simulated neutron per batch, and we disregard it for simplicity purposes.

3. RESULTS

In OpenMC we simulated a simplified PWR reactor core with constant 4.95%_{wt} enriched fuel at 900 K with added 3.1%_{wt} gadolinia (Gd (not Gd₂O₃) in fuel (UO₂ + Gd₂O₃)) in the outermost fuel element ring; reactor core consists of 37 17 × 17 fuel elements. Cooling water is simulated with added boric acid and is simplified to have constant 560 K temperature and 0.74773 $\frac{g}{cm^3}$ density without boric acid. Boric acid used for mixing in the coolant is assumed to have the same molar concentration as water (molar concentration of the mixture is kept constant). This model is used as a simple framework for comparing different algorithms. We performed multiple critical density search simulations and compared results

from the critical density iteration (CDI) algorithm described in this paper to all four current criticality search methods used in OpenMC using conventional numeric root finding methods: Bisection, Brent-h [5] (hyperbolic extrapolation), Brent-q [6] (quadratic extrapolation), and Ridder [7] method.

3.1. Current Algorithms

Using current OpenMC search algorithms we varied the number of neutrons per batch (N_M) and number of batches (M). The search algorithms tolerance for effective multiplication factor was set at $k_{eff} = 1.00000 \pm 0.00100$ or 100 pcm (per cent mille = 10^{-5}). All algorithms require bounds for critical densities, which were set from 0 ppm to 5000 ppm of boron (B^{10} and B^{11}) in the reactor coolant (not boric acid). We assume the total number density of coolant molecules remains constant; water H_2O molecules are replaced by boric acid (H_3BO_3), so the mixture molar volume is unchanged.

Results on the left side of Figure 1 show that the current implemented search algorithms perform similarly. In search algorithms we set the tolerance for $\Delta k_{eff} = 100$ pcm (light blue area in Figure 1), which was the lowest value, for which each of the algorithms were performed in reasonable time (6 hours for the longest bisection algorithm on 96 CPU cores). Each simulation consisted of 300 neutron batches (M), with varying neutron batch sizes (N_M). For each result final more accurate k_{eff} was verified by a longer test simulation with 10^7 neutrons. The grey area shows additional 1σ test simulation uncertainty.

Boric acid concentration shown on the right side of Figure 1 represents the final concentration provided by the search algorithms. Current algorithms do not return any uncertainty in critical density, due to their implementation and unawareness of any uncertainties. To achieve higher accuracy, more neutrons need to be simulated, otherwise the statistical uncertainty of k_{eff} is too high, and the algorithms cannot converge properly. If two subsequent steps yield similar results, the algorithm cannot distinguish the stochastic deviation in k_{eff} from convergence and the resulting critical density gets stuck. Therefore, these search algorithms are not ideal for MC codes because they ignore statistical uncertainty and assume the value function (in our case k_{eff}) is noise-free. For this reason, even with high number of simulated neutrons the critical value rarely converges to the true value. With increasing number of simulated neutrons in a calculation step this effect remains present, but its magnitude diminishes.

Figure 1. Effective multiplication factor k_{eff} and boric acid concentrations C obtained from simulations using different search algorithms in relation to total and batchwise number of neutrons.

3.2. Critical Density Iteration Results

Similar to the previous section, we performed several simulations with the newly implemented CDI algorithm. Again, we varied the number of neutrons per batch (N_M) and the number of batches (M). Results shown on the left side of Figure 2 represent the simulated effective multiplication factor k_{eff} and its uncertainty during test simulations (≈ 30 pcm). Any further deviation is a result of CDI's convergence. New algorithm shows performance close to theoretically optimal performance (grey area) for our test case with 10^7 neutrons, when using more than 10000 neutrons per batch. Simulated batches were split up into 10 generations to reduce the transient effects of on-the-fly nuclide concentrations changes. Simulations with fewer than $5 \cdot 10^6$ are not able to reliably converge to within the desired accuracy of 100 pcm, which is close to the theoretical limit of $1 \cdot 10^6$ ($\sigma_{k_{eff}} \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_M M}} < 100$ pcm).

Figure 2. Effective multiplication factor k_{eff} and boric acid concentrations C obtained from critical density iteration in relation to total and batchwise number of neutrons.

Result comparison between CDI (Figure 2) and current algorithms (Figure 1) show that CDI achieves better results with fewer required extra simulated neutrons. Critical density in CDI clearly converges with increasing number of simulated neutrons, whereas other search algorithms struggle with fine accuracy when the statistical deviation of k_{eff} is greater than the effect on k_{eff} due to changing critical density. Figure 2 also shows that extreme cases with low number of neutrons per batch do not perform well, because stronger effect of subsequent correlated statistical deviations between two small batches (end of Section 2.3.1). On the other hand, if the number of batches would be too low, then any changes in concentration would be high and the approximation of linear relation between k_{eff} and C would not hold at that scale.

Figure 3 represents CDI's deviation from criticality $\Delta k_{eff} = |k_{eff} - 1|$ in relation to number of neutrons per batch and the number of batches. As expected, the accuracy improves with increasing total number of simulated neutrons (batches $\cdot \frac{\text{neutrons}}{\text{batch}}$). Results were calculated only once for each combination of number of batches and number of neutrons per batch, in order to show stochastic effects. Approximately two thirds of the results lie within σ_C of C_{avg} , which is expected for normally distributed results. The general trend of higher accuracy with more simulated neutrons is clear.

In Figure 3 CDI's accuracy $\Delta C = |C - C_{avg}|$, and its uncertainty σ_C is shown, where C_{avg} is the weighted

average critical boric acid concentration from all simulations (3160.9 ± 1.8 ppm). Because ΔC is uncertain, Δk_{eff} is uncertain as well; the quantities are correlated. The resulting boric acid coefficient of reactivity is approximately $-5 \frac{\text{pcm}}{\text{ppm}}$, which is confirmed by obtaining the average across $\frac{\Delta k_{eff}}{\Delta C}$. Boric acid coefficient of reactivity also explains deviations in k_{eff} due to uncertain concentrations provided by search algorithms in Figures 1 to 3.

Figure 3. Simulated $\Delta k_{eff} = |k_{eff} - 1|$, $\Delta C = |C - C_{avg}|$, σ_C , and $\frac{\Delta C}{\sigma_C}$ using critical density iteration in relation to number of neutrons per batch and the number of batches during the search algorithm.

Again, CDI struggles when $L_{abs,mucs}$ has high uncertainties: either due to either small nuclide concentrations, or low number of neutrons per batch ($N_M < 10000$ in Figures 2 and 3). For this reason, we recommend simulating at least 50000 neutrons per batch, though the value may vary based on the problem's geometry and the desired nuclide densities. Finally, in Table I we grouped all the differentiating qualities between current algorithms and CDI.

Table I. Comparison of three differentiating qualities between current algorithms and critical density iteration.

	Current algorithms	Critical Density Iteration
Statistical noise sensitivity	High	Low*
Convergence rate	Fast	Faster
Number of required simulations	5 – 10	1

*Provided the number of neutrons per batch is adequate (model dependent; ≈ 50000).

3.2.1. Other improvements

Besides the improved algorithm, we also implemented a few other improvements to the criticality search in OpenMC. Criticality search now supports finding critical densities for one or more nuclides of the same element and for molecules (groups of nuclides), with support for material mixing. This partial enrichment based material mixing is also usable in mixed material building, i.e., boric acid diluted in water, and nuclear fuels with added gadolinia based burnable absorbers.

Currently, the convention for boric acid dilution calculation is to ignore the miniscule changes of concentrations of oxygen and hydrogen due to perturbations of boric acid concentrations. H_3BO_3 has 1 more hydrogen and 2 more oxygen atoms which in small concentrations on the order of few ppm do not affect the total H and O concentrations significantly and consequently k_{eff} . The new material mixing feature allows for proper calculation of all nuclide densities in the mixture, which can be important in high precision simulations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We implemented a new algorithm called Critical Density Iteration (CDI) into OpenMC, which intertwines the search algorithm within a single simulation. Based on the neutron balance equation, changes in nuclide densities are calculated and refined by the Kalman filter for measuring a scalar constant. This method allows for 5 – 10 times faster simulations and more reliable estimations of critical concentration, by also considering previous steps within the algorithm's intertwined simulation.

Newly implemented CDI was compared to all four previously implemented criticality search methods in OpenMC: Bisection, Brent-h [5], Brent-q [6], and Ridder [7] methods. For comparing methods, we used a simplified PWR model that served as a framework for testing. Results show that CDI achieves comparable results with fewer required extra simulated neutrons compared to current methods. Although more thorough testing still needs to be done, we estimate that CDI requires to simulate 5 to 10 times fewer neutrons to achieve the same accuracy. The main advantages of CDI are, that it is more resilient to stochastic deviations resulting from the Monte Carlo method, and is more appropriate for use in higher precision simulations. CDI and all other search methods struggle with low concentrations due to low absorption rate on flagged nuclides, which are then lost in the statistical noise of the simulation.

Besides CDI, we also implemented partial enrichment based material mixing in OpenMC for:

- one or more nuclides within a material, and
- molecules (groups of nuclides), with support for sub-material mixing.

CDI is intended to be implemented into future public version of OpenMC. We invite you to participate in testing and validating the algorithm with your own projects, by contacting the corresponding author.

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